

Interview's Protocol

Questions for the Interview

1. How old are you?
2. Which state and city do you live in?
3. What is the classification of your visual impairment?
4. Do you use screen readers, if yes, which one?
5. What computing higher education degree are you getting/do you have?
6. Which educational institution do/did you go to?
7. Have you seen UML content during any course of your higher education? Do you know UML diagrams?
8. Were the educational methodologies or strategies used to teach the course that addressed the UML content useful?
9. Were accessible technologies used in the process of learning the UML diagrams?
10. Were tools utilized for the creation and development of the UML diagrams? If yes, did those tools have accessibility functions?
11. Which functions would be desired to make the tools that create UML diagrams accessible?
12. Would you like it if the tools for the creation of UML diagrams were more accessible?

Explain that we want to develop a tool for the Python programming language and present the requirements of said tool.

13. Do those requirements make sense? Do you think it is lacking something? What would be the best way to present those functions?

14. How would you rate this interview? Give us your feedback.